

Polymetallic complexes. Part-CI : Dimeric and tetrameric Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes with tetra and octadentate azodye ligands

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Abstract : Six dimeric and six tetrameric complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with one tetradentate and one octadentate ligand having $\text{O} \curvearrowright \text{N} - \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \text{O} \end{array} \right)$ and $\left(\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \text{O} \end{array} \right) - \text{N} \curvearrowright \text{O} - \text{O} \curvearrowright \text{N} - \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ \text{O} \end{array} \right)$ donor atoms have been synthesized and characterized by elemental analysis, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, IR, electronic, NMR spectra and X-ray diffraction studies. The Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes are octahedral, Cu^{II} complexes are distorted octahedral and a tetrahedral geometry has been assigned to Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes.

Keywords : Azodye complexes, polymetallic complexes.

Introduction

Study of polydentate azodyes as ligands to form polynuclear transitional and non-transitional complexes is of present interest. Azodyes have been widely used in various fields and technologies like textiles, leather, plastics, paper, laser liquid crystalline displays and ink jet printers¹⁻³. They are also used in food⁴, drug, cosmetic and photochemical productions⁵. The pharmacological and chemotherapeutic activity of azodyes are well recognised as they possess antibacterial, antifungal, antiseptic, herbicidal, pesticidal and anticancerial properties⁶. Azodyes are also used as indicators in chemistry. Keeping all these important properties of azodyes in mind the synthetic organic chemists have been inspired to prepare broad spectrum drugs from the azodyes obtained from aromatic and heterocyclic amines. We now focus our attention to the preparation of completely new polydentate azodyes ligands and to study their complexation behaviour with divalent transitional metal ions⁷. The present paper reports the synthesis of two new polydentate azodyes (one octadentate Fig. 1 and one tetradentate Fig. 2) and twelve tetrameric and dimeric metal complexes.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Results and discussion

The metal complexes synthesized (Table 1) have the compositions $[M_4LC1_2(H_2O)_{14}]$, $[M'_4LC1_2(H_2O)_6]$, $[M_2L'Cl_2(H_2O)_7]$ and $[M'_2L'Cl_2(H_2O)_3]$; where $M = Co^{II}$, Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} ; $M' = Zn^{II}$, Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} ; $C_{34}H_{22}O_8N_4$ (Fig. 1) and $C_{13}H_8O_8N_4$ (Fig. 2).

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the complexes

Compd.	Colour	Analysis (%) :			μ_{eff} (B.M.)
		Found/(Calcd.)			
		Metal	Nitrogen	Chlorine	
LH ₆ (C ₃₄ H ₂₂ O ₈ N ₄)	Brown	-	9.12 (8.9)	-	
L'H ₃ (C ₁₃ H ₈ O ₈ N ₄)	Reddish brown	-	16.09 (15.09)	-	
[Co ₄ LC1 ₂ (H ₂ O) ₁₄]	Deep red	20.21 (19.9)	4.80 (4.7)	6.08 (5.9)	5.00
[Co ₂ L'Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₇]	Brown	17.86 (17.5)	8.48 (8.2)	10.76 (10.5)	5.10
[Ni ₄ LC1 ₂ (H ₂ O) ₁₄]	Red	20.11 (19.8)	4.81 (4.7)	6.09 (5.9)	3.00
[Ni ₂ L'Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₇]	Red	17.78 (17.5)	8.49 (8.2)	10.77 (10.4)	3.10
[Cu ₄ LC1 ₂ (H ₂ O) ₁₄]	Brown	21.45 (21.2)	4.72 (4.5)	5.99 (5.6)	1.80
[Cu ₂ L'Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₇]	Brown	19.00 (18.8)	8.37 (8.1)	10.61 (10.3)	1.81
[Zn ₄ LC1 ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	Yellow	24.94 (24.6)	5.34 (5.1)	6.77 (6.5)	-
[Zn ₂ L'Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₃]	Yellow	21.76 (21.4)	9.32 (9.1)	11.82 (11.5)	-
[Cd ₄ LC1 ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	Brown	36.36 (36.1)	4.53 (4.3)	5.74 (5.5)	-
[Cd ₂ L'Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₃]	Brown	32.35 (32.1)	8.06 (7.8)	10.22 (9.9)	-
[Hg ₄ LC1 ₂ (H ₂ O) ₆]	Yellow	50.48 (50.2)	3.52 (3.4)	4.47 (4.2)	-
[Hg ₂ L'Cl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₃]	Brown	46.05 (45.8)	6.43 (6.2)	8.15 (7.9)	-

LH₆ = 2,2'-Bis(3'-carboxy-4'-hydroxyphenylazo)- α -dinaphthol.

L'H₃ = 2'-(3'-Carboxy-4'-hydroxyphenylazo)-4,6-dinitrophenol.

All the complexes are amorphous in nature, have high melting points, and are insoluble in common organic solvents but sparingly soluble in DMF. The non-electrolytic nature of the complexes in DMF is shown from the low conductance values (4.1–5.9 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-2}$).

In the IR spectra of the ligands, broad bands observed at 3399–3421 cm^{-1} may be attributed to intramolecular O–H...N hydrogen bonding. Disappearance of these bands in the metal chelates indicates the bonding⁸ of the phenolic -OH groups to the metal atoms. The band at 1488 cm^{-1} (LH₆) and at 1537 cm^{-1} (L'H₃) can be assigned to phenolic C–O vibration and in the metal chelates these bands appear at $\sim 1437 \text{cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1486 \text{cm}^{-1}$ respectively indicating the bonding of ligands to the metal ions through the phenolic oxygen atoms⁹. The sharp band for the ligands at 1590 cm^{-1} (LH₆) and at 1600 cm^{-1} (L'H₃) can be attributed to $\nu(-N=N-)$ vibration and in the metal complexes these bands appear at 1585 cm^{-1} and at 1605 cm^{-1} which indicates the bonding of one of the azo nitrogen atoms to the metal ions¹⁰. In the ligands asymmetric (COO⁻) and symmetric (COO⁻) bands appear at 1622 cm^{-1} and 1448 cm^{-1} (LH₆) and 1625 cm^{-1} and 1434 cm^{-1} (L'H₃) respectively and these bands appear in the metal complexes at ~ 1649 – 1434cm^{-1} and 1604 – 1386cm^{-1} with a difference ($\Delta\nu$) of $\sim 215 \text{cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 218 \text{cm}^{-1}$ supporting monodentate nature of carboxylate group¹¹. In the metal chelates broad bands appear at 3390–3421 cm^{-1} and 839–833 cm^{-1} followed by sharp peak at ~ 724 – 761cm^{-1} assigned to -OH stretching, rocking and wagging vibrations respectively indicating the presence of co-ordinated water molecules in the complexes¹². The conclusive evidence of bonding of the ligands to the metal ions is proved by the appearance of bands at ~ 524 (M–O) and 485 (M–N)¹³.

In the electronic spectra of Co^{II} complexes, four ligand field bands are observed at 8135 (8240), 16320 (16565), 20252 (20445) and 32150 (32250) cm^{-1} . The first three bands can be attributed to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F) (\nu_1)$, $\rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F) (\nu_2)$ and $\rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P) (\nu_3)$ transitions respectively and the fourth band is assigned to a CT band. The ligand field parameters like $Dq = 818.50$ (832.50) cm^{-1} , $B = 811.13$ (819.33) cm^{-1} , $\beta_{35} = 0.835$ (0.844) cm^{-1} ; $\nu_2/\nu_1 = 2.006$ (2.010) and $\sigma = 19.72\%$ (18.51%) suggest an octahedral geometry for the complexes¹⁴. In the electronic spectra of Ni^{II} complexes, four ligand field bands are observed at 10241 (10265), 17582 (17670), 25120 (25168) and 32570 (32775) cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F) (\nu_1)$, $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F) (\nu_2)$, $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P) (\nu_3)$ and CT transition respectively in an octahedral geometry. The ligand field parameters like $Dq = 1024.10$ (1026.50) cm^{-1} , $B = 798.60$ (802.86) cm^{-1} , $\beta_{35} = 0.767$ (0.771) cm^{-1} , $\nu_2/\nu_1 = 1.716$ (1.721) and $\sigma = 30.36\%$ (29.70%) also confirm an octahedral geometry for the complexes¹⁵. The

Note

electronic spectra of copper(II) complexes show one broad band at $\sim 13460\text{--}14520\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with maxima at $\sim 14320\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition in support of a distorted-octahedral configuration of the complexes¹⁶.

The ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectra of the ligands (LH_6) and ($\text{L}'\text{H}_3$) were recorded in CDCl_3 . The complex pattern observed at $\delta = 7.001\text{--}8.425$ ($\text{L}'\text{H}_3$) and $\delta = 7.761\text{--}8.705$ ($\text{L}'\text{H}_3$) corresponds to 16 and 5 phenyl protons respectively. The sharp singlet observed at $\delta = 10.274$ (LH_6) and $\delta = 10.120$ ($\text{L}'\text{H}_3$) corresponds to four and two phenolic protons respectively. The small peak observed at $\delta = 13.691$ (LH_6) can be assigned to two carboxyl proton. This was not observed in ($\text{L}'\text{H}_3$) as the recording was not done in this region (Graph 1 and Graph 2).

The Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes exhibit magnetic moments ~ 5.0 , ~ 3.0 and ~ 1.8 B.M. indicating the presence of three, two and one unpaired electron respectively¹⁷.

The XRD (powder pattern) of the complexes $[\text{Co}_4\text{LCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{14}]$ and $[\text{Cu}_4\text{LCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{14}]$ were indexed using LSUCRIPC software (courtesy R. Garvev, North Dakota University, USA through Sri L. D. Pradhan, Scientist (Retired), IMMT, Bhubaneswar). The unit cell parameters were calculated by a computer from the 2θ values (Graphs 3 and 4). The direct constant parameters like a , b , c , α , β , γ and V (volume) were calculated from the 2θ values and are given in Table 2. The density of the

Graph 1

Graph 2

Graph 3. XRD graph for $[\text{Co}_4\text{LCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{14}]$

Graph 4. XRD graph for $[\text{Cu}_4\text{LCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{14}]$

complexes were determined by the flotation method in a saturated solution of KBr, NaCl and benzene separately. The number of formula units per unit cell (n) is calculated which agrees well with the suggested tetragonal and triclinic structure of the complexes^{18,19} respectively.

The Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are suggested to be four-coordinated having tetrahedral geometry based upon analytical, conductance and IR spectral data.

Hence the azodye (LH_6) behave as bis-tetradentate (octadentate) and ($\text{L}'\text{H}_3$) behaves as bis-bidentate (tetradentate) ligands forming tetrameric and dimeric complexes being bonded through azo nitrogens, phenolic oxygens and carboxylic oxygen atoms.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of B.D.H. or E. Merck grade Metal, carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and chlorine were estimated by standard methods. Conductivity measurement in DMF was made using Toshniwal CL 01-06 conductivity bridge. Magnetic moment was measured at room temperature by Gouy method IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on an IFS 66U spectrophotometer, electronic spectra ($10^{-2} M$ in DMF) using Hilger-Watt uvispeck spectrophotometer and NMR spectra on a Jeol GSX 400 with CDCl_3 as solvent and TMS as internal standard and X-ray diffraction (powder pattern) of the complexes were recorded by LSUCRIPC software using a IBM compatible PC-AT 80486, 66 MHz.

Table 2. X-Ray diffraction data of complexes

Compd.	2 θ values (in degrees)	Unit cell parameters	Density (g/cc)	<i>n</i>	Probable geometry
[Co ₄ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₁₄]	12.78, 12.88, 12.96, 13.01, 13.75, 14.00, 14.51, 15.80, 16.34, 17.16, 18.34, 19.21, 21.51, 22.05, 22.98, 24.88, 26.52, 27.97, 28.94, 32.54, 35.92, 39.72, 41.54, 43.14, 48.26, 54.44, 56.88, 64.74, 71.52	<i>a</i> = 25.653 Å <i>b</i> = 27.841 Å <i>c</i> = 10.276 Å α = 90.00° β = 90.00° γ = 90.00° <i>V</i> = 7339.32 cc	1.05	4	Tetragonal
[Cu ₄ LCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₁₄]	13.70, 14.63, 15.65, 16.16, 17.65, 18.27, 19.06, 20.49, 21.51, 22.27, 23.68, 25.29, 27.80, 28.41, 29.89, 32.54, 34.41, 40.78, 43.14, 50.17, 55.08, 60.36, 75.78, 80.40, 98.30	<i>a</i> = 12.856 Å <i>b</i> = 13.961 Å <i>c</i> = 6.790 Å α = 88.652° β = 104.755° γ = 112.380° <i>V</i> = 1086.06 cc	1.05	0.5	Triclinic

Preparation of the ligand :

Both the azodyes were synthesized by the coupling reaction of the diazonium chlorides obtained from 5-aminosalicylic acid (0.02 mol, 3.04 g) and (0.01 mol, 1.52 g) separately with alkaline solution of α -dinaphthol (0.01 mol, 2.86 g) and 2,4-dinitrophenol (0.01 mol, 1.36 g) at 0–5 °C.

Preparation of the complexes :

The metal chlorides in ethanol were mixed separately with ethanolic solution of the ligands in 4 : 1 and 2 : 1 molar ratio respectively. The resulting solutions were then heated to ~60 °C for about one hour in a heating mantle. On cooling pH of the solution was raised to ~7. The solid complexes thus separated were then washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried in vacuum.

Conclusion :

Basing upon the above observation, the following tetra and dimeric structures (Figs. 3 and 4) have been proposed for the complexes.

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

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